

ELECTRIC DRIVE CONTROLLERS

EM-TECH

Eco-Driving with reduced energy consumption

Improve safety during traction and braking through advanced control systems

CHALLENGES AND SOLUTION:

Novel control solutions leveraging fast electric motor dynamics and EM-TECH innovations have been developed to improve BEV safety and efficiency. Using either model predictive control (MPC) or AI-based methods, these algorithms can be adapted for vehicles with in-wheel or onboard motors. For safety, wheel slip control strategies were designed for both braking and traction: in ABS, IWMs provide rapid torque modulation to reduce braking fluctuations and stopping distance, while a nonlinear MPC optimally distributes motor and friction brake torques. Reinforcement learning-based controllers were also trained via the AVL_VSM/Simulink toolchain to manage tire slippage and enhance grip on low-friction surfaces. In terms of energy savings, various IWM switching strategies—from rule-based to optimisation-based approaches incorporating

pulse-and-glide techniques—were proposed to optimise motor winding selection and minimise energy consumption.

IMPACT & NEXT STEPS:

Future efforts will focus on validating the proposed control methods through real-world testing and closer collaboration with industrial and research partners. These activities will demonstrate its effectiveness beyond simulation, ensuring reliable performance under practical operating conditions. Ultimately, this work aims to advance electric mobility solutions that are more efficient, safer, and more comfortable, supporting their wider adoption in next-generation transportation systems.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the nonlinear model predictive controller with brake blending strategy

Segment	Baseline IWM (wh/km)	EMTECH IWM + e-gear shifting management (wh/km)	Energy/distance Improvement (%)
A (2F-IWM)	160.3	143.09	10.73
B (2F-IWM)	164.8	153.5	6.86
C (2R-IWM)	169.3	157.8	6.78
D (2R-IWM)	158.66	144.5	8.93
Small Van (2F-IWM)	222.17	205.09	7.69
M (2R-IWM)	262.9	237.17	9.80
M (4-IWM)	273.75	245.27	10.41

Energy consumption per distance (Wh/km) and percentage difference in energy efficiency for various vehicle segments and drivetrains across WLTP driving cycle.

Figure 2: The results presented in the tables indicate consistent reductions in energy consumption per unit distance for e-gear IWM relative to the baseline IWM from ELA, with improvements ranging from 7.35% to 11.12%, depending on the specific vehicle configuration. The accompanying figures illustrate the braking manoeuvre employing e-gear IWMs as the anti-lock braking system.

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